

University of Bucharest Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics

Master: Databases and Software Technologies

Project
Database security

Coordinating teacher:

Lectr.Dr.L.Marin

Masterand:

Voicu Cristian Valentin

Contents

1. Introduction	4
1.1 Presentation of the model and its rules	4
1.2 Conceptual Diagram.....	5
1.3 Relational Schema.....	5
1.4 Creating Tables (separate script)	6
2. Data encryption.....	6
2.1 Encryption	6
2.2 Decryption.....	7
2.3 Hash (MD5)	8
3. Auditing activities on the database.....	9
3.1 Standard Audit	12
3.2 Audit triggers.....	13
3.3 Audit policies.....	14
4. Managing database users and computational resources	14
4.1 Designing the management configuration of identities in the database (process-user matrix, entity-process matrix, entity-user matrix)	14
4.1.1 The main users of the application.....	14
4.1.2 The processes within the application	14
4.1.3 Process – User Matrix	15
4.1.4 Identification of entities by modeling the application data	15
4.1.5 Entity – Process Matrix	16
4.1.6 Entity-User Matrix.....	17
4.2 Implementation of identities management within the database.....	17
5. Privileges and roles	20
5.1 System and object privileges	20
5.1.1 System privileges	20
5.1.2 Object privileges	22
5.2 Hierarchies of privileges.....	23
5.3 Privileges on dependent objects.....	24
5.4 Roles.....	25
6. Applications on databases and data security.....	26

6.1 The context of the application	26
6.2 SQL Injection	26
7. Data masking.....	32

1. Introduction

1.1 Presentation of the model and its rules

To carry out this project, I chose as the theme the management of a chain of fitness centers that offer training services as well as highlighting the results at certain time intervals.

The database operations are focused on customers. They have the possibility to purchase subscriptions with different durations and prices. Each training session is carried out individually, with or without the guidance of a fitness trainer.

The database stores data specific to trainers, the gyms where they work, and the available fitness programs.

The usefulness of this model is to monitor results, both the results of individual clients and the fitness center chain, as results/cost reports for clients and profit/cost reports for the gym chain can be generated.

The database contains 10 tables. Within them, 2 constraints were applied, the PRIMARY KEY constraint and the FOREIGN KEY constraint.

The PRIMARY KEY constraint uniquely identifies each record. Thus, in each of the 10 tables, there is a column, the first column, defined as the PRIMARY KEY. The existence of the unique identifier at the table level allows operations on any record when operations are desired on it and only it.

The FOREIGN KEY constraint establishes a foreign key relationship between a column in a table and a column in a referenced table. In tables that contain data about service purchases and customer outcomes, foreign keys are used to generate individual reports about each customer.

1.2 Conceptual Diagram

1.3 Relational Schema

Customers (customer_id, first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, date_of_birth, gender, has_health_issues)

Results (result_id, customer_id, body_fat, weight, height, age, entry_date)

Subscriptions (subscription_id, max_number_sessions, sb_title, sb_description, with_trainer, max_number_days, price)

Customers_Subscriptions(customer_subscription_id, subscription_id, customer_id, start_date, end_date, price)

Sessions (session_id, customer_subscription_id, location_id, trainer_id, start_date, end_date)

Trainers (trainer_id, first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, birth_date, gender)

Contracts (contract_id, trainer_id, start_date, end_date, salary)

Locations (location_id, location_capacity, city_id, address)

Cities (city_id, state_id, city_name)

States (state_id, state_name)

1.4 Creating Tables (separate script)

2. Data encryption

2.1 Encryption

Personal data (email and phone_number) of the **tb_trainers** table will be encrypted (AES- 128, PAD_PKCS5, CHAIN_CBC) and stored in the **tb_trainers_crypt** table as follows:

- for female coaches, the records will be encrypted with the key **cheie_f**
- for male coaches the records will be encrypted with the key **cheie_m**

The two keys will be automatically generated and stored in the database.

I will be using the sequence **tb_secv_idcheie** and the **tb_chei** (idcheie#,cheie,tabel) table

And the **criptare_trainer_email_phone** procedure without parameters.

I am displaying the two keys used for encryption:


```
307
308   end loop;
309   commit;
310   end;
311 //
312
313 execute criptare_trainer_email_phone;
314
315 select * from tb_chei;
316 select email, phone_number, gender from tb_trainers;
317 select * from tb_trainers_crypt;
318
319 create table tb_trainers_crypt;
```

ID_CHEIE	CHEIE	TABEL
1	19F427EEAA432C9C665B28D3D38CE0634	tb_trainers
2	2C905CA64CD29713B0F50B91E825DC488	tb_trainers

Script Output x Query Result x

Script Output x | All Rows Fetched: 2 in 0.01 seconds

Compiler - Log

Messages | Logging Page | Statements | Compiler x

I am displaying the data in the table unencrypted.

I am displaying the encrypted table data.

2.2 Decryption

Personal data (email and phone_number) from **tb_trainers_decrypt** table will be decrypted. The procedure **decriptare_trainer_email_phone** will be used without the parameters and the keys stored in the **tb_chei** table, in the same order (female, male). The decrypted data is stored in the **tb_trainers_decrypt** table.

I display the decrypted data in the table.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a PL/SQL script in the Query Builder. The script includes a loop that decrypts phone numbers and emails for trainers. Below the script, the 'Script Output' window shows the results of the query, which is a table with three columns: EMAIL_DECRYPT, PHONE_DECRYPT, and GENDER. The table contains five rows of data.

EMAIL_DECRYPT	PHONE_DECRYPT	GENDER
1 VictoriaLane231@t.dwb1.com	5044458466	female
2 LydiaJackson232@t.dwb1.com	9785601725	female
3 DanielCooper233@t.dwb1.com	3076332086	male
4 JuliaJackson234@t.dwb1.com	5213137791	female
5 WilliamClarke235@t.dwb1.com	5909432028	male

2.3 Hash (MD5)

A function is created `tb_rezum_md5` that returns the HASH (MD5) summary for the registration in the `TB_TRAINERS` table, corresponding to the trainer with `trainer_id` equal to 10. The result is stored in the variable bind `tb_rezumat1`.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a PL/SQL script in the Query Builder. The script defines a function `tb_rezum_md5` that concatenates registration details and returns an MD5 hash. Below the script, the 'Script Output' window shows the results of the query, which is a table with one row containing the concatenated registration details and the resulting MD5 hash.

TB_REZUMAT1
E69FB06611CBC19BC6B1E9DA063E82B2

Updating the trainer's phone number where `trainer_id` equals 10 and create a new summary in the `TB_rezumat2` variable.

TB_Rezumat1 : E69FB06611CBC19BC6B1E9DA063E82B2

TB_Rezumat2 : 92347CFD854FFE9EE92E9769A63549EE

After updating the data, the function returns a different hash.

3. Auditing activities on the database

The audit will be achieved by connecting the predefined **HR** user to the Pluggable database **Orclpdb**.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a SQL script in the Worksheet area:

```

200
201 alter session set container = CDB$ROOT;
202 alter system set audit_trail=db, extended scope=spfile;
203 --restart oracle ( @sqlplus)
204 --shutdown immediate
205 --startup
206 show parameter audit_trail;
207
208

```

The Script Output window shows the following messages:

```

Session altered.

System SET altered.

```

The Query Result window displays the output of the `show parameter audit_trail;` command:

NAME	TYPE	VALUE
audit_trail	string	DB

The Dbms Output window shows the task completion message: "Task completed in 0.062 seconds".

The screenshot shows a terminal window titled "SQL Plus" with the following text:

```

SQL*Plus: Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production on Wed Jun 7 09:52:53 2023
Version 19.3.0.0.0

Copyright (c) 1982, 2019, Oracle. All rights reserved.

Enter user-name: sys as sysdba
Enter password:

Connected to:
Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production
Version 19.3.0.0.0

SQL> shutdown immediate;
Database closed.
Database dismounted.
ORACLE instance shut down.
SQL> startup;
ORACLE instance started.

Total System Global Area 2566910648 bytes
Fixed Size          9269944 bytes
Variable Size       754974720 bytes
Database Buffers    1795162112 bytes
Redo Buffers        7503872 bytes
Database mounted.
Database opened.
SQL>

```

Connections: local sys, secbd_jfr, userstest22_jfr

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

200
201 alter session set container = CDB$ROOT;
202 alter system set audit_trail=db, extended scope=spfile;
203 --restart oracle ( sqlplus)
204 --shutdown immediate
205 --startup
206 show parameter audit_trail;
207
208

```

Script Output x | Query Result x | Task completed in 0.204 seconds

System SET altered.

NAME	TYPE	VALUE
audit_trail	string	DB
audit_trail	string	DB, EXTENDED

Dbms Output: Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x userstest22_jfr x

Compiler - Log

Compiler

Connections: local sys, secbd_jfr, userstest22_jfr

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

200
201 alter session set container = CDB$ROOT;
202 alter system set audit_trail=db, extended scope=spfile;
203 --restart oracle ( sqlplus)
204 --shutdown immediate
205 --startup
206 show parameter audit_trail;
207 audit select table;
208 desc dba_stmt_audit_opts;
209

```

Script Output x | Query Result x | Task completed in 2.055 seconds

Audit succeeded.

Name	Null?	Type
USER_NAME		VARCHAR2 (128)
PROXY_NAME		VARCHAR2 (128)
AUDIT_OPTION	NOT NULL	VARCHAR2 (40)
SUCCESS		VARCHAR2 (10)
FAILURE		VARCHAR2 (10)

Dbms Output: Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x userstest22_jfr x

Compiler - Log

Compiler

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a SQL script with the following lines:

```

214
215 alter user hr account unlock;
216
217
218 alter user hr account unlock;
219 alter user hr identified by hr;
220
221 select username, account_status, password
222 from dba_users where lower(username) like 'hr';
223

```

The Query Result pane shows the following output:

USERNAME	ACCOUNT_STATUS	PASSWORD
1 HR	OPEN	(null)

The Dbms Output pane shows the execution details: "secbd_ifr x userstest22_ifr x".

3.1 Standard Audit

A "select" order is executed on the "SECBD_IFR.TB_TRAINERS" table.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The main window displays a SQL script with the following line:

```

1 select * from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers;

```

The Query Result pane shows the following output:

TRAINER_ID	FIRST_NAME	LAST_NAME	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	BIRTH_DATE	GENDER	PASSWORD
52	179 David	Lane	DavidLane179@t.dwb1.com	3611624152	05-APR-86	male	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C4588DFBC1558F0D02F0
53	180 Elaine	Lane	ElaineLane180@t.dwb1.com	9132013898	15-AUG-89	female	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C4588DFE183C67F3FF6D8
54	182 Barney	Mills	BarneyMills182@t.dwb1.com	7974481839	15-APR-85	male	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C45888BF1A7C9CF0D17D2
55	184 Amanda	Green	AmandaGreen184@t.dwb1.com	6501246000	26-JAN-85	female	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C458882174DDC4D4E225
56	186 Amanda	Bates	AmandaBates186@t.dwb1.com	8999447013	24-JUN-94	female	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C45884A2968704C58D82E
57	188 Danielle	Hall	DanielleHall188@t.dwb1.com	9391074956	04-MAR-73	female	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C458817D29DEB14419D2

The Dbms Output pane shows the execution details: "secbd_ifr x userstest22_ifr x".

Display the number of select orders executed:

- by each user for each table
- by each user regardless of the table
- total number of select orders regardless of user and table
- I will analyze only the tables **tb_trainers**, **tb_locations** and **tb_customers**

3.2 Audit triggers

This section is reserved for future development. The current version reflects the state of the project at the time of its original academic submission.

3.3 Audit policies

This section is reserved for future development. The current version reflects the state of the project at the time of its original academic submission.

4. Managing database users and computational resources

4.1 Designing the management configuration of identities in the database (process-user matrix, entity-process matrix, entity-user matrix)

4.1.1 The main users of the application

The application users are:

Customers – email, phone number

Trainers – email, phone number

Application administrator – email

Each of these types of users has the email address as identification attribute. An additional identification attribute will be the phone number.

4.1.2 The processes within the application

Within the application there are the following processes:

P1: Manage trainers

P2: Manage customers

P3: Manage trainer contracts

P4: Manage customer results

P5: Manage subscriptions

P6: Manage customer subscriptions

P7: Manage training sessions

P8: Manage locations

P9: View trainers

P10: View customers

P11: View trainer contracts

P12: View customer results

P13: View subscriptions

P14: View customer subscriptions

P15:View training sessions

P16:View locations

4.1.3 Process - User Matrix

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16
Customers									X			X	X	X	X	X
Trainers				X		X	X		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Administrator	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

4.1.4 Identification of entities by modeling the application data

The system is a platform for managing a chain of fitness gyms.

Within the system, I can configure the subscriptions which the customers can purchase to benefit from fitness training services.

A subscription may include one or more training sessions that take place at a location with or without guiding a fitness trainer. Customers who have health problems can participate in strict training sessions under the guidance of a trainer.

The gyms are located in different states and cities, the number of operational gyms will be determined by the volume of subscriptions, sessions and the capacity of each location.

The trainers are hired with contracts and they offer training services and monitor the results of the clients.

Relational Schema:

Customers (customer_id, first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, date_of_birth, gender, has_health_issues)

Results (result_id, customer_id, body_fat, weight, height, age, entry_date)

Subscriptions (subscription_id, max_number_sessions, sb_title, sb_description, with_trainer, max_number_days, price)

Customers_Subscriptions(customer_subscription_id, subscription_id, customer_id, start_date, end_date, price)

Sessions (session_id, customer_subscription_id, location_id, trainer_id, start_date, end_date)

Trainers (trainer_id, first_name, last_name, email, phone_number, birth_date, gender)

Contracts (contract_id, trainer_id, start_date, end_date, salary)

Locations (location_id, location_capacity, city_id, address)

Cities (city_id, state_id, city_name)

States (state_id, state_name)

4.1.5 Entity - Process Matrix

	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11	P12	P13	P14	P15	P16
Customers		C,R,U,D		R		R				R						
Results				C,R,U,D								R				
Subscriptions					C,R,U,D	R							R			
Customers_Subscriptions						C,R,U,D	R							R		
Sessions							C,R,U,D								R	
Trainers	C,R,U,D		R				R		R							
Contracts			C,R,U,D								R					
Locations							R	C,R,U,D								R
Cities							R	C,R,U,D								R
States							R	C,R,U,D								R

Legend: C=create, R=read, U=update, D=delete

4.1.6 Entity-User Matrix

	Customers	Trainers	Administrators
Customers	R	R	C,R,U,D
Results	R	C,R,U,D	C,R,U,D
Subscriptions	R	R	C,R,U,D
Customers_Subscriptions	R	C,R,U,D	C,R,U,D
Sessions	R	C,R,U,D	C,R,U,D
Trainers	R	R	C,R,U,D
Contracts		R	C,R,U,D
Locations	R	R	C,R,U,D
Cities	R	R	C,R,U,D
States	R	R	C,R,U,D

Legend: C=create, R=read, U=update, D=delete

4.2 Implementation of identities management within the database

Creating the following users: an administrator, two trainers and two customers.

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface. The 'Connections' pane on the left lists various database tables. The main window displays a SQL script in the 'Worksheet' area, which includes the creation of a user and a query to list users. The 'Query Result' pane shows the output of the query, listing seven users with their authentication types and expiration dates.

```

64 create user tb_customer2 identified by tb_customer2 password expire;
65 grant create session to tb_customer2;
66
67
68 desc dba_users;
69 select username, AUTHENTICATION_TYPE, ACCOUNT_STATUS, EXPIRY_DATE, CREATED
70 from dba_users
71 order by created desc;
72

```

USERNAME	AUTHENTICATION_TYPE	ACCOUNT_STATUS	EXPIRY_DATE	CREATED
1 TB_CUSTOMER2	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
2 TB_ADMIN	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
3 TB_TRAINER1	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
4 TB_TRAINER2	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
5 TB_CUSTOMER1	PASSWORD	EXPIRED	06-JUN-23	06-JUN-23
6 USERTEST22_IFR	PASSWORD	OPEN	02-DEC-23	05-JUN-23
7 SECBD_IFR	PASSWORD	OPEN	30-NOV-23	03-JUN-23

I am creating user profiles for trainers and customers with CPU consumption per call not to exceed 90 seconds, having the right to a single session at a given time, the lifetime of a password is 30 days and to be able to insert the password wrong for a maximum of 5 times.

Connections: local sys, secbd_jfr, usertest22_jfr, TB_TRAINERS

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

79 create profile tb_profile_customers limit
80   cpu_per_call 9000
81   sessions_per_user 1
82   password_life_time 7
83   failed_login_attempts 5;
84
85 desc dba_profiles;
86 select * from dba_profiles where lower(profile) like 'tb_*';
87

```

Script Output x | Query Result x | Query Result 1 x

All Rows Fetched: 34 in 0.096 seconds

PROFILE	RESOURCE_NAME	RESOURCE_TYPE	LIMIT	COMMON	INHERITED	IMPLICIT
1 TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS	COMPOSITE_LIMIT	KERNEL	DEFAULT	NO	NO	NO
2 TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS	COMPOSITE_LIMIT	KERNEL	DEFAULT	NO	NO	NO
3 TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS	SESSIONS_PER_USER	KERNEL	1	NO	NO	NO
4 TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS	SESSIONS_PER_USER	KERNEL	1	NO	NO	NO
5 TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS	CPU_PER_SESSION	KERNEL	DEFAULT	NO	NO	NO
6 TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS	CPU_PER_SESSION	KERNEL	DEFAULT	NO	NO	NO
7 TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS	CPU_PER_CALL	KERNEL	9000	NO	NO	NO

Dbms Output: Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x usertest22_jfr x

Compiler - Log

Compiler

Connections: local sys, secbd_jfr, usertest22_jfr, TB_TRAINERS

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

87
88 desc dba_users;
89 select username, profile from dba_users where lower(username) like 'tb_*';
90
91 alter user tb_trainer1 profile tb_profile_trainers;
92 alter user tb_trainer2 profile tb_profile_trainers;
93 alter user tb_customer1 profile tb_profile_customers;
94 alter user tb_customer2 profile tb_profile_customers;
95

```

Script Output x | Query Result x | Query Result 1 x | Query Result 2 x | Query Result 3 x

All Rows Fetched: 5 in 0.023 seconds

USERNAME	PROFILE
1 TB_ADMIN	DEFAULT
2 TB_TRAINER1	TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS
3 TB_TRAINER2	TB_PROFILE_TRAINERS
4 TB_CUSTOMER1	TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS
5 TB_CUSTOMER2	TB_PROFILE_CUSTOMERS

Dbms Output: Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x usertest22_jfr x

Compiler - Log

Compiler

Temporarily locking the access to the database for the user **tb_customer1**.

Unlocking the access to the database for the user **tb_customer1**.

I create 3 consumption groups: **trainers**, **customers**, **other_groups** with CPU consumption quotas 40%, 20% and 10%.

5. Privileges and roles

5.1 System and object privileges

5.1.1 System privileges

The "**select any table**" privilege is granted for the user "**tb_admin**".

```
Select Command Prompt - sqlplus tb_trainer1/tb_trainer11@orclpdb
SQL> disconnect
Disconnected from Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production
Version 19.3.0.0.0
SQL> connect tb_admin/tb_admin1@orclpdb
Connected.
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers;
select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers
*
ERROR at line 1:
ORA-00942: table or view does not exist

SQL> |
```

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. On the left, the 'Connections' pane shows a tree view with 'secbd_ifr' and 'usertest22_ifr' expanded. The 'Tables (Filtered)' section lists 'MATERIE', 'REZOLVA', 'STUD 1', 'STUDENT', and 'TEMA'. The 'Reports' section lists 'All Reports', 'Analytic View Reports', 'Data Dictionary Reports', 'Data Modeler Reports', 'OLAP Reports', 'TimesTen Reports', and 'User Defined Reports'. The main 'Worksheet' area contains the following SQL script:

```
182 |
183 | REVOKE select on secbd_ifr.tb_customers from tb_trainer1;
184 |
185 | grant select any table to tb_admin;
186 |
187 |
188 |
189 |
190 |
```

The 'Script Output' pane shows the following messages:

```
Grant succeeded.
Revoke succeeded.
Grant succeeded.
```

The 'Dbms Output' pane shows the session information:

```
secbd_ifr x usertest22_ifr x
```

The 'Compiler - Log' pane is empty.

```
Command Prompt - sqlplus tb_trainer1/tb_trainer11@orclpdb
SQL> disconnect
Disconnected from Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production
Version 19.3.0.0.0
SQL> connect tb_admin/tb_admin1@orclpdb
Connected.
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers;
select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers
*
ERROR at line 1:
ORA-00942: table or view does not exist

SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers;

COUNT(*)
-----
         438

SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers;

COUNT(*)
-----
       3872

SQL>
```

5.1.2 Object privileges

The "Select" privilege is granted on the `SECBD_IFR.TB_Customers` table for the user `tb_trainer1`.

```
Command Prompt - sqlplus tb_trainer1/tb_trainer11@orclpdb
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers;
select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers
*
ERROR at line 1:
ORA-00942: table or view does not exist

SQL>
```


5.2 Hierarchies of privileges

The `select` privilege on the `sector_ifr.tb_customers` table is revoked for the user `tb_trainer1`.

5.3 Privileges on dependent objects

This section is reserved for future development. The current version reflects the state of the project at the time of its original academic submission.

5.4 Roles

Granting the role of `afisare_date` to the user `tb_trainer2`.

The role allows the `select` privilege on the `sector_ifr.tb_customers` and `sector_ifr.tb_locations` tables.

The screenshot shows the Oracle SQL Developer interface. The 'Connections' pane on the left shows the 'secbd_ifr' and 'usertest22_ifr' schemas. The 'Worksheet' pane contains the following SQL script:

```
187  
188 :create role afisare_date;  
189 :grant afisare_date to tb_trainer2;  
190 :grant select on secbd_ifr.tb_customers to afisare_date;  
191 :grant select on secbd_ifr.tb_locations to afisare_date;  
192  
193 :SELECT * FROM DBA_role_privs;  
194  
195
```

The 'Query Result' pane displays the output of the `SELECT * FROM DBA_role_privs;` query:

GRANTEE	GRANTED_ROLE	ADMIN_OPTION	DELEGATE_OPTION	DEFAULT_ROLE	COMMON	INHERITED
1 USERTEST22_IFR	RESOURCE	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
2 SYS	AFISARE_DATE	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO
3 PDB_DBA	CONNECT	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
4 HR	RESOURCE	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
5 TB_TRAINER2	AFISARE_DATE	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
6 SECBD_IFR	CONNECT	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO
7 USERTEST22_IFR	CONNECT	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO

The 'Dbms Output' pane shows the execution of the script:

```
secbd_ifr x usertest22_ifr x
```

The screenshot shows a Command Prompt window titled 'Command Prompt - sqlplus tb_trainer1/tb_trainer11@orclpdb'. The output is as follows:

```
-----  
COUNT(*)  
-----  
3872  
  
SQL> disconnect  
Disconnected from Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production  
Version 19.3.0.0.0  
SQL> connect tb_trainer2/tb_trainer2@orclpdb  
ERROR:  
ORA-28001: the password has expired  
  
Changing password for tb_trainer2  
New password:  
Retype new password:  
Password changed  
Connected.  
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers;  
select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_trainers  
*  
  
ERROR at line 1:  
ORA-00942: table or view does not exist  
  
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_customers;  
  
COUNT(*)  
-----  
3872  
  
SQL> select count(*) from secbd_ifr.tb_locations;  
  
COUNT(*)  
-----  
70  
  
SQL>
```

6. Applications on databases and data security

6.1 The context of the application

This section is reserved for future development. The current version reflects the state of the project at the time of its original academic submission.

6.2 SQL Injection

I am testing the security of the data by securing and validating the login operations of the users in the **TB_Trainers** table. For this, a new column will be added to **TB_Trainers** which will include their encrypted login passwords.

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with the following components:

- Connections:** A tree view on the left showing database objects like PHONE_NUMBER, BIRTH_DATE, GENDER, and TB_TRAINERS_CRYPT.
- Worksheet:** A SQL script in the center with the following code:


```

421 end loop;
422 END;
423
424 execute run_pachet_mascare2;
425
426 select * from tb_trainers1;
427
428 ALTER TABLE tb_trainers ADD Password varchar(255);
429
430
431
432
433
434
435

```
- Script Output:** A window below the worksheet showing the message: "Table TB_TRAINERS altered." and "Task completed in 0.923 seconds".
- Dbms Output:** A window at the bottom left showing connection details for "secbd_jfr" and "usertest22_jfr", including a buffer size of 20000 and several asterisks representing output.
- Compiler - Log:** A window at the bottom right, currently empty.

The screenshot shows the SQL Developer interface with the following components:

- Connections:** A tree view on the left showing database objects like PHONE_NUMBER, BIRTH_DATE, GENDER, and TB_TRAINERS_CRYPT.
- Worksheet:** A SQL script in the center with the following code:


```

433
434 create or replace procedure criptare_parola is
435 cheie varchar2(6) := 'parola';
436 raw_text raw(250);
437 raw_cheie raw(250);
438 mod_operare pls_integer;
439 rezultat raw(250);
440 cursor c_trainers is select trainer_id from tb_trainers;
441 parola varchar2(100) := 'secret_password';
442 parola2 varchar2(100) := 'secret_password';
443 cnt number :=1;

```
- Script Output:** A window below the worksheet showing the message: "the application administrator or DBA for more information." and "Procedure CRIPTARE_PAROLA compiled".
- Dbms Output:** A window at the bottom left showing connection details for "secbd_jfr" and "usertest22_jfr", including a buffer size of 20000.
- Compiler - Log:** A window at the bottom right, currently empty.

Connections: local sys, secbd_jfr, usertest22_jfr

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

454 cnt := cnt + 1;
455
456 UPDATE tb_trainers SET password = resultat WHERE trainer_id = rec.trainer_id;
457 --dbms_output.put_line (resultat);
458 end loop;
459 commit;
460 end;
461
462 execute criptare_parola;
463
464 select * from tb_trainers;

```

Script Output x Query Result x

Task completed in 0.196 seconds

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Dbms Output: Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x usertest22_jfr x

Compiler - Log

M... Logging Page Statements Compiler

| Line 462 Column 25 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

Connections: local sys, secbd_jfr, usertest22_jfr

Worksheet: Query Builder

```

454 cnt := cnt + 1;
455
456 UPDATE tb_trainers SET password = resultat WHERE trainer_id = rec.trainer_id;
457 --dbms_output.put_line (resultat);
458 end loop;
459 commit;
460 end;
461
462 execute criptare_parola;
463
464 select * from tb_trainers;

```

Script Output x Query Result x

SQL | Fetched 50 rows in 0.007 seconds

TRAINER_ID	FIRST_NAME	LAST_NAME	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	BIRTH_DATE	GENDER	PASSWORD
1	Lydia	Ross	LydiaRoss1008t.dwb1.com	1037391919	23-AUG-79	female	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C45841FA9A5069FD5471
2	Michael	Hall	MichaelHall1101t.dwb1.com	9026171316	30-SEP-78	male	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C458A0915E42DEED983E
3	Beverley	Hall	BeverleyHall1102t.dwb1.com	7601908127	07-FEB-75	female	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C458A66B36EDA0D42FFF
4	Daniel	Clarke	DanielClarke1038t.dwb1.com	2762164928	01-MAR-76	male	A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C4580C39D267106865C4

Dbms Output: Buffer Size: 20000

secbd_jfr x usertest22_jfr x

Compiler - Log

M... Logging Page Statements Compiler

| Line 464 Column 27 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

Connections | Welcome Page | local sys | secbd_fr | userstest22_fr | TB_TRAINERS

Worksheet | Query Builder

```

466 create or replace FUNCTION criptare_parola_v2(parola2 IN VARCHAR2) RETURN VARCHAR2 as
467 cheie varchar2(6) := 'parola';
468 raw_text raw(250);
469 raw_cheie raw(250);
470 mod_operare pls_integer;
471 rezultat raw(250);
472 begin
473 mod_operare := dbms_crypto.encrypt_des + dbms_crypto.pad_zero + dbms_crypto.chain_ecb;
474 raw_text := utl_i18n.string_to_raw ( parola2, 'AL32UTF8');
475 raw_cheie := utl_i18n.string_to_raw (cheie, 'AL32UTF8');
476 rezultat :=dbms_crypto.encrypt(raw_text, mod_operare,raw_cheie);

```

Script Output x | Query Result x

Task completed in 0.089 seconds

Function CRIPTARE_PAROLA_V2 compiled

Dbms Output | Buffer Size: 20000

```

secbd_fr x | userstest22_fr x
COUNT(*) FROM tb_trainers WHERE email='LydiaRoss100@t.dwh1.com' AND PAROLA=criptare_parola('secret_password!')
CAREA A REUSII

```

Compiler - Log

M... | Logging Page | Statements | Compiler

| Line 479 Column 2 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

Connections | Welcome Page | local sys | secbd_fr | userstest22_fr | TB_TRAINERS

Worksheet | Query Builder

```

504
505 CREATE OR REPLACE PROCEDURE VERIFICA_LOGIN (P_EMAIL VARCHAR2,P_PAROLA VARCHAR2) AS
506 v_ok NUMBER(4) :=-1;
507 BEGIN
508 EXECUTE IMMEDIATE 'SELECT COUNT(*) FROM tb_trainers WHERE email='''||P_EMAIL||'''' AND password='''||P_PAROLA||'''' INTO v_ok;
509 DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('SELECT COUNT(*) FROM tb_trainers WHERE email='''||P_EMAIL||'''' AND password='''||P_PAROLA||''''');
510 IF v_ok=0 THEN
511 DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('VERIFICAREA A ESUAT');
512 ELSE
513 DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('VERIFICAREA A REUSII');
514 END IF;
515 END;
516
517

```

Script Output x | Query Result x

Task completed in 0.084 seconds

Procedure VERIFICA_LOGIN compiled

Dbms Output | Buffer Size: 20000

```

secbd_fr x | userstest22_fr x

```

Compiler - Log

Compiler

| Line 516 Column 2 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

I observe that the first execution was successfully validated, while the second failed, because I used the same password from the first execution. The passwords of the two trainers are different.

I observe that the executions were successfully validated although at the first attempt the user did not know the password, and in the second, he knew neither the email address, nor the password.

Connections

- local sys
- secbd_fr
- usertest22_fr
- TB_TRAINERS

Worksheet Query Builder

```

523
524 CREATE OR REPLACE PROCEDURE VERIFICA_LOGIN_SAFE (P_EMAIL VARCHAR2,P_PAROLA VARCHAR2) AS
525 v_ok NUMBER(4) :=-1;
526 BEGIN
527 EXECUTE IMMEDIATE 'SELECT COUNT(*) FROM tb_trainers WHERE email=:ema AND password=:pa' INTO v_ok USING P_EMAIL,P_PAROLA;
528
529 IF v_ok=0 THEN
530     DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('VERIFICAREA A ESUAT');
531 ELSE
532     DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('VERIFICAREA A REUSIT');
533 END IF;
534 END;
535

```

Script Output x Query Result x

Task completed in 0.053 seconds

Procedure VERIFICA_LOGIN_SAFE compiled

Dbms Output Buffer Size:20000

secbd_fr x usertest22_fr x

Compiler - Log

Compiler

Connections

- local sys
- secbd_fr
- usertest22_fr
- TB_TRAINERS

Worksheet Query Builder

```

531 ELSE
532     DBMS_OUTPUT.PUT_LINE('VERIFICAREA A REUSIT');
533 END IF;
534 END;
535 /
536
537 .execute VERIFICA_LOGIN_SAFE ('LydiaRoss100@t.dwbi.com', 'A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C45841FA8A5069FD5471');
538 .execute VERIFICA_LOGIN_SAFE ('MichaelHall101@t.dwbi.com', 'A8F93E166371E8C0C75E5C40B1E6C45841FA8A5069FD5471');
539
540 .execute VERIFICA_LOGIN_SAFE ('LydiaRoss100@t.dwbi.com'--, 'no_ideea');
541 .execute VERIFICA_LOGIN_SAFE ('no_ideea' OR 1=1 --, 'no_ideea');
542

```

Script Output x Query Result x

Task completed in 0.044 seconds

PL/SQL procedure successfully completed.

Dbms Output Buffer Size:20000

secbd_fr x usertest22_fr x

VERIFICAREA A REUSIT

VERIFICAREA A ESUAT

Compiler - Log

Compiler

| Line 537 Column 1 | Insert | Modified | Windows: C

I observe that the executions were not successfully validated because at the first attempt the user did not know the password, and in the second, he knew neither the email address, nor the password.

7. Data masking

Performing data masking for the **email** column in the **TB_trainers** table.

I use the package `package_mascare2` and the function `f_mascare2` to mask the email addresses in the `TB_TRAINERS` table.

I perform the export of the table by applying the masking function from the package in the director [dirsecbd_ifr](#).


```
Command Prompt

E:\WINDOWS.X64_193000_db_home\bin>expdp secbd_ifr/secbd_ifr@orclpdb tables=tb_trainers, remap_data=secbd_ifr.tb_trainers.email:pachet_mascare2.f_mascare2 directory=dirsecbd_ifr dumpfile=FISEXPORT.dmp

Export: Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production on Mon Jun 5 21:27:02 2023
Version 19.3.0.0.0

Copyright (c) 1982, 2019, Oracle and/or its affiliates. All rights reserved.

Connected to: Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production
Starting "SECBD_IFR"."SYS_EXPORT_TABLE_01": secbd_ifr/*****@orclpdb tables=tb_trainers, remap_data=secbd_ifr.tb_trainers.email:pachet_mascare2.f_mascare2 directory=dirsecbd_ifr dumpfile=FISEXPORT.dmp
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/TABLE_DATA
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/INDEX/STATISTICS/INDEX_STATISTICS
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/STATISTICS/TABLE_STATISTICS
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/STATISTICS/MARKER
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/TABLE
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/CONSTRAINT/CONSTRAINT
. . exported "SECBD_IFR"."TB_TRAINERS" 38.98 KB 438 rows
Master table "SECBD_IFR"."SYS_EXPORT_TABLE_01" successfully loaded/unloaded
*****
Dump file set for SECBD_IFR.SYS_EXPORT_TABLE_01 is:
E:\TMP\SECBD_IFR\FISEXPORT.DMP
Job "SECBD_IFR"."SYS_EXPORT_TABLE_01" successfully completed at Mon Jun 5 21:27:44 2023 elapsed 0 00:00:36

E:\WINDOWS.X64_193000_db_home\bin>
```

I perform the data import from the director `dirsecbd_ifr` in the table `TB_TRAINERS1`.

```
Command Prompt

Job "SECBD_IFR"."SYS_EXPORT_TABLE_01" successfully completed at Mon Jun 5 21:27:44 2023 elapsed 0 00:00:36

E:\WINDOWS.X64_193000_db_home\bin>impdp secbd_ifr/secbd_ifr@orclpdb directory=dirsecbd_ifr dumpfile=FISEXPORT.DMP TABLES=tb_trainers remap_table=tb_trainers:tb_trainers1

Import: Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production on Mon Jun 5 21:30:28 2023
Version 19.3.0.0.0

Copyright (c) 1982, 2019, Oracle and/or its affiliates. All rights reserved.

Connected to: Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition Release 19.0.0.0.0 - Production
Master table "SECBD_IFR"."SYS_IMPORT_TABLE_01" successfully loaded/unloaded
Starting "SECBD_IFR"."SYS_IMPORT_TABLE_01": secbd_ifr/*****@orclpdb directory=dirsecbd_ifr dumpfile=FISEXPORT.DMP TABLES=tb_trainers remap_table=tb_trainers:tb_trainers1
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/TABLE
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/TABLE_DATA
. . imported "SECBD_IFR"."TB_TRAINERS1" 38.98 KB 438 rows
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/CONSTRAINT/CONSTRAINT
ORA-31684: Object type CONSTRAINT:"SECBD_IFR"."TB_TRAINERS_UNIQUE_EMAIL" already exists

ORA-31684: Object type CONSTRAINT:"SECBD_IFR"."TB_TRAINERS_ID_PK" already exists

Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/INDEX/STATISTICS/INDEX_STATISTICS
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/STATISTICS/TABLE_STATISTICS
Processing object type TABLE_EXPORT/TABLE/STATISTICS/MARKER
Job "SECBD_IFR"."SYS_IMPORT_TABLE_01" completed with 2 error(s) at Mon Jun 5 21:30:57 2023 elapsed 0 00:00:28

E:\WINDOWS.X64_193000_db_home\bin>
```

Connections | Welcome Page | local sys | secbd_fr | userstest22_fr | TB_TRAINERS1

Worksheet | Query Builder

```

421 cursor crs is select first_name, last_name, email from tb_trainers;
422 BEGIN
423 for rec in crs loop
424   dbms_output.put_line (rec.first_name || ' ' || rec.last_name || ' ' || pachat_mascare2.f_mascare2(rec.email));
425 end loop;
426 END;
427
428 execute run_pachat_mascare2;
429
430 select * from tb_trainers1;
431

```

Script Output x | Query Result x | Fetched 50 rows in 0.07 seconds

TRAINER_ID	FIRST_NAME	LAST_NAME	EMAIL	PHONE_NUMBER	BIRTH_DATE	GENDER
1	Lydia	Ross	L*****	1037381919	23-AUG-79	female
2	Michael	Hall	M*****	9026171316	30-SEP-78	male
3	Beverley	Hall	B*****	7601908127	07-FEB-75	female
4	Daniel	Clarke	D*****	2762164928	01-MAR-76	male

Dbms Output | Buffer Size: 20000

```

secbd_fr x userstest22_fr x
Lydia Ross L*****
Michael Hall M*****
Beverley Hall B*****
Daniel Clarke D*****
Elaine Nelson E*****

```

Compiler - Log

M... | Logging Page | Statements | Compiler |

| Line 430 Column 28 | | Insert | | Modified | Windows: C